

Photogrammetry for morphometric analysis of anhydrite-gypsum weathering zones

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¹
Abstract

In anhydrite-gypsum weathering zones, two distinct types of dome-shaped landforms, anhydrite hydration features and gypsum tumuli undergo dynamic morphological changes driven by probable volumetric expansion processes. To capture and quantify these changes, we applied a combined UAV-based and terrestrial photogrammetry approach at sites in Canada and Spain (Fig. 1). High-resolution 3D models and digital datasets allowed us to extract key morphometric parameters, such as landform dimensions, cavity volumes, and fracture patterns. Our results highlight photogrammetry as an effective and precise method for monitoring and analyzing the evolution of landforms in evaporite environments.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the weathering zone of anhydrite-gypsum rock, we documented two distinct types of landforms: anhydrite hydration landforms (Dingwall; Fig. 2A) and gypsum tumuli (Sorbas; Fig. 2B). These features are predominantly dome-like, reaching up to 2 meters in height and extending over 10 meters in length. Some also contain inner cavities. The processes responsible for their formation cause volume expansion and deformation within the rock [1,2].

Due to their rapid morphological changes over years or decades, we employed an efficient and time-effective approach, photogrammetry, to analyze their morphometric characteristics. Using both aerial and terrestrial photogrammetry, we generated high-resolution models for three study sites in Canada and Spain. The digital datasets allowed us to compute key morphometric

parameters, providing valuable insights into the formation and evolution of these landforms.

Figure 1. Study area of the Dingwall abandoned gypsum quarry (Nova Scotia, Canada) and Sorbas gypsum plateau (Andalusia, Spain).

II. METHODS

We applied photogrammetry using two models of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs: DJI Phantom 4, DJI Air 2s), two models of digital camera, and a GPS receiver with RTK for ground control and checkpoint measurements. Aerial photogrammetry was applied in the Dingwall area twice to analyze rock deformations in time. These works resulted in 2.5D models, orthophotomaps and Digital Surface Models (DSMs) of the quarry bottom, as well as 3D models of anhydrite hydration landforms and gypsum tumuli. For the modeling landforms we included both outer rock surface and their cavities to describe. Image processing was conducted using Metashape, a Structure from Motion (SfM)-based software [3]. Additionally, digital terrain models (DTMs) and orthophotomaps were analyzed using ArcGIS to extract and interpret morphometric parameters. They include planar

dimensions of the outer landforms extent like long and short axis, but also of the inner cavity like true length, true width. Among these parameters are relative height of the landforms, height of the chamber (cavity), entrance width/height, thickness of detached rock layer and azimuth of elongation of the long axis and true length. For some cavities we computed volume and area. We also documented fracture pattern, computed circularity coefficient, bulge degree.

III. RESULTS

We generated high-resolution 3D models of both the broader landscape and individual landforms, achieving a ground resolution of <1 cm/pixel. They represent rock relief created during weathering processes at both sites presenting its dimensions, shape and structural features. In the Dignwall site and the Sorbas site our cartographic works mapped more than a few hundred landforms. The average dimensions of anhydrite hydration landforms were 5.25 m (long axis) × 3.38 m (short axis), while gypsum tumuli averaged 2.37 m × 1.78 m. Generally dimensions of both hydration landforms and gypsum tumuli are similar, but maximum long axis of the first one is larger (Table 1). Described landforms are positive part of the weathering zone characterized by some regularities that was deduced on the basis of linear regression lines and Pearson's correlation coefficient. One of the main relations for hydration landform development is as follows $b = 67a$ (b – short axis, a – long axis), on the other hand for gypsum tumuli is $b = 78a$. In general, their elongation is described by their coefficient of circularity, $C = (a-b)/a$, and has an average value of 0.33 for hydration landforms and 0.24 for gypsum tumuli.

Table 1. Selected morphometric parameters related to anhydrite hydration landforms and gypsum tumuli [1,4,5]

Anhydrite hydration landforms	
Name of the parameter	Minimum-maximum [m]; average value [m]; number of measurements
Length (long axis)	1.86–23.05; 5.25; 74
Width (short axis)	0.91–9.01; 8.38; 74
Relative height	0.33–2.09; 0.83; 74
Long axis (cavity)	0.70–8.87; 3.15; 52
Short axis (cavity)	0.33–5.10; 2.04; 40
Height of the chamber	0.28–1.35; 0.64; 41
Gypsum tumuli	
Name of the parameter	Minimum-maximum [m]; average value [m]; number of measurements
Length (Long axis)	0.35–8.40; 2.37; 100
Width (short axis)	0.25–7.95; 1.78; 100
Relative height	0.04–1.30; 0.23; 142
True length	0.60–6.96; 2.27; 66
True width	0.45–5.01; 1.65; 66
Height of the chamber	0.07–1.00; 0.28; 66

Analyzing part of the anhydrite weathering zone in Dingwall from 2018 to 2023 gave us difficulty specifying elevation differences, only qualitative changes were possible to identify.

Figure 2. Studied landforms; A - hydration landform at former gypsum quarry in Dingwall (Canada); B – gypsum tumulus recognized at karst zone near Sorbas (Spain; AJ is inside)

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Our results demonstrate that photogrammetry is an efficient and highly accurate tool for analyzing anhydrite-gypsum weathering zones. The combination of UAV-based and terrestrial photogrammetry enables detailed morphometric assessment,

aiding in the documentation and monitoring of these rapidly evolving landforms. This approach offers a valuable method for studying dynamic geomorphic processes in karst and evaporite environments.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Jarzyna, A.J., Babel, M., Vladi, F., Ługowski, D., 2023. Hydration caves and cavities from the recent weathering zone of anhydrites at Dingwall (Nova Scotia, Canada). *Geomorphology* 433, 1-21.
- [2] Calaforra, J.M., Pulido-Bosch, A., 1999. Genesis and evolution of gypsum tumuli. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms* 24, 919-930. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2023.108667>
- [3] Westoby, M.J., Brasington, J., Glasser, N.F., Hambrey, M.J., Reynolds, J.M., 2012. ‘Structure-from Motion’ photogrammetry: A low-cost, effective tool for geoscience applications. *Geomorphology* 179, 300-314 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2012.08.021>
- [4] Jarzyna, A., Babel, M., Ługowski, D., Vladi, F., 2022. Morphology of dome- and tepee-like landforms generated by expansive hydration of weathering anhydrite: a case study at Dingwall, Nova Scotia, Canada. *Applied Sciences* 12, 7374: 1-34.
- [5] Jarzyna, A., Babel, M., Czajkowsja, M., Ługowski, D., 2024. Morphometry and morphology of the gypsum tumuli from the Sorbas karst region, SE Spain. *Geomorphology* 465, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2024.109403>